

Bouveret Syndrome: Case Report and Literature Review

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ABSTRACT

Bouveret syndrome is a very rare form of gastric outlet obstruction following the passage of a gallstone from the gallbladder to the duodenum or pylorus through a bilioenteric fistula. ¹ This rare syndrome was first described in 1896 by Leon Bouveret, a French physician, which since then bears his name. A classic Rigler's triad of dilated stomach, pneumobilia, and ectopic stone appearing as a filling defect in the duodenum seen on a CT scan is virtually pathognomonic of the Bouveret's syndrome. The primary therapeutic goal is gallstone retrieval. ^{1,2}

KEYWORDS: Bouveret syndrome, gastric obstruction, cholecystoduodenal fistula.

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INTRODUCTION

Bouveret syndrome was first described by Bartolin in 1654 and Bouveret in 1896. This type of biliary ileus represents the least common (1-3% of cases).³

Bouveret syndrome frequently presents with symptoms of gastric obstruction, however, the clinical picture of this syndrome may not be specific. The patient's clinical data depend on the degree of obstruction, the site of stone impaction, among other factors.

There are recognized risk factors for the development of Bouveret syndrome such as a history of cholelithiasis, female sex, age over 60 years, mainly, in addition, recurrent cases of cholecystitis result in erosion and necrosis of the gallbladder wall, which leads to the formation of a cholecysto-duodenal fistula.³ By the age of 75, approximately 35% of women and 20% of men have developed gallstones, thus the frequency of this diagnosis. The majority of these patients do well, but complications occur in around 6% of them.⁴

Contrast-enhanced computed tomography can provide a sensitivity of 90-93% and a specificity of up to 100% in the case of gallstone ileus; Rigler's triad: pneumobilia, intestinal obstruction, ectopic gallstone, can be observed on radiological imaging in only up to 21% of cases.¹¹

Due to the rarity of this pathology, a therapeutic protocol for these cases has not yet been standardized. Currently, it

considers fragmentation (YAG laser lithotripsy, mechanical fragmentation) as the first line, especially in those patients with high surgical risk, reserving surgery only for highly selected patients. ³

Surgical options include enterotomy (gastrotomy or duodenotomy) and stone extraction alone, concomitant enterotomy and stone extraction with cholecystectomy and excision of the cholecysto-enteric fistula (one-stage procedure) or enterotomy and stone extraction with interval cholecystectomy and excision of the cholecysto-enteric fistula after 4–6 weeks (two-stage procedure). ^{7,8}

CASE PRESENTATION

A 66-year-old woman presented to the emergency department with and 3-year history of arterial hypertension in management with losartan 50 mg every 24 hours.

Her condition began a week history of diffuse abdominal pain with nausea and vomiting with an intensity of 7/10, colic-like, that increase in the last 24 hours then she decided to go to emergency unit. Abdominal examination revealed, right upper quadrant tenderness, distension, absent bowel sounds and no peritoneal signs. Laboratory values were within the normal range. Abdominal radiography showed no signs of subdiaphragmatic free air or evidence of intestinal occlusion. (figure 1).

Figure 1. Abdominal X ray

Contrast computed tomography of the abdomen shows gallstone in duodenum (Figure 2) pneumobilia and gastric distention (figure 3, 4), showing Rigler's triad, that is specific

to gallstone ileus, consisting of small bowel obstruction, pneumobilia and ectopic gallstone.

Figure 2. Axial view of computed tomography shows gallstone in duodenum.

Figure 3. Coronal view of computed tomography shows gallstone in duodenum.

Figure 4. Coronal view of computed tomography shows pneumobilia and gastric distention.

The patient underwent laparotomy; the stone was successfully extracted through gastrotomy. (figure 5) The postoperative course remained uneventful, 3 days after surgery the liquid diet was given and the patient was

discharged after seven days without any complication. At follow-up visit, 3 weeks postoperatively, the patient was recovering well without complications. At her subsequent consultation, she reported no obstructive symptoms

Figure 5. Duodenum gallstone

DISCUSSION

Bouveret's syndrome is a very rare complication of cholelithiasis, characterised by gastric outlet obstruction caused by an impacted gallstone in the pylorus or proximal duodenum after its passage through a bilioenteric fistula. Gallstones may migrate via bilioenteric fistula into various parts of the digestive tract, including the ileocecal region (50%–90%), jejunum and ileum (20%–40%) and less commonly, the stomach or duodenum (<5 %) in which cases it is called Bouveret's syndrome.⁸

Bouveret's syndrome is typically seen in elderly women, with a gender ratio 2:1 and with a median age of 74.1 years. Patients most frequently present with abdominal pain, nausea and/or emesis (63%), haematemesis (24%), fever (5%), or occasionally with jaundice (3%). It is associated with

mortality rates as high as 30% although recent data shows an improvement to approximately 12%.⁹

Possible complications of Bouveret's syndrome encompass gastrointestinal bleeding, bowel perforation and migration of gallstones into more distal bowel segments, where they can no longer be reached endoscopically and may cause an ileus.

Intestinal obstruction due to impacted gallstones may occur in up to 15% of cases, particularly in the presence of adhesions or strictures due to previous abdominal surgery.

A multidisciplinary approach is necessary for effective care, with endoscopic intervention as the primary therapeutic option.

Although endoscopy is of low morbidity, in the majority of cases it is unsuccessful and surgery is required for definitive management of Bouveret's syndrome in 91% of cases.¹⁰

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CONFLICTS OF INTEREST

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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INFORMED CONSENT STATEMENT

Written informed consent was obtained from the patient for publication of this case report and accompanying images. A written copy is available upon request.

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